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ERRATUM

In the article “*Comparative Clinical Outcomes of Patients with Low and Preserved Left Ventricular Ejection Fraction Undergoing Off-Pump Coronary Artery Bypass Surgery – A Single-Center Study*”, originally published as **Version 1** in *The Insight*, Volume 08, Number 03 (July–September), pages 466–470 (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17752600](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17752600)), the author name “**Shadequl**” was incomplete.

The correct author name is “**Shadequl Islam**”.

No other aspects of the article, including authorship order, contributions, or content, have been changed.

A corrected version of the article has been published as **Version 2** (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18093791](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18093791)). The original version remains available for transparency.